

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development

D6.10 - Report on synergies with other projects

WP6 – Open

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable serves primarily as a reference document among consortium partners to support activities of the project related to synergies. It can also be used by other similar projects to draw from our review of potential networks for synergies as well as plan joint activities with relevant projects and initiatives.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This report outlines the DIAMOND project's strategy for developing structured, meaningful synergies with other research initiatives—particularly its Horizon Europe sister projects—to maximise scientific impact, enhance cooperation, and strengthen the relevance of climate-policy modelling. Building on the project's core vision of openness, interdisciplinarity, and co-creation, the report establishes how collaboration with aligned projects can support the project's ambition to advance next-generation integrated assessment modelling (IAM) and to contribute robustly to European and global climate policy processes. Expanding on the plan, we highlight the synergies established so far, which include 35 joint scientific publications, 33 joint conference presentations, the organisation of two webinars with contributions from other projects, the co-organisation of two side events at COP28 and COP30, and active participation in the MAIA project's activities and Climate Research Communication Network.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO SENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA' COOPERATIVA	IT	
SEURECO	SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL	FR	
UM	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	NL	
ESMIA	ESMIA CONSULTANTS INC.	CA	
USMF	THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC	US	
UMD	UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND	US	
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH	
ETH	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	CH	
UNIBAS	UNIVERSITAT BASEL	CH	
Imperial	IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	UK	
Oxford	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK	
UCL	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UK	

Executive Summary

This report first outlines DIAMOND's strategy for developing structured, meaningful synergies with other research initiatives—particularly its Horizon Europe sister projects—to maximise scientific impact, enhance cooperation, and strengthen the relevance of climate-policy modelling. Building on DIAMOND's core vision of openness, interdisciplinarity, and co-creation, the report establishes how collaboration with aligned projects can support the project's ambition to advance next-generation integrated assessment modelling (IAM) and to contribute robustly to European and global climate policy processes.

The report's goal is to identify the opportunities and reports on established efforts for coordination that leverage complementary expertise, avoid duplication of effort, and foster a shared scientific foundation across the IAM community. It sets out the assumptions and principles guiding this coordination. Drawing on early consultations within the consortium, as well as input from the European Commission and CINEA, the report maps two categories of potential partners: (a) sister projects focused on improving IAMs, and (b) other relevant initiatives that can enhance DIAMOND's outreach, transdisciplinary character, and policy resonance.

By examining thematic and geographical complementarities, data and platform interoperability, and shared stakeholder networks, the report identifies concrete spaces for collaboration. These include harmonising modelling efforts, ensuring access to open modelling infrastructures such as the IAM PARIS platform, and creating joint activities in communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

After providing an action plan intended to guide DIAMOND's engagement with the broader research ecosystem, reinforcing cooperation as a central mechanism for strengthening scientific support to climate policymaking, this deliverable ultimately reports on our achievements in the direction of the outlined strategy and principles for meaningful collaboration and synergies. These notably include 35 scientific publications, 33 joint conference presentations, the organisation of two webinars with contributions from other projects, the co-organisation of two side events at COP28 and COP30, and active participation in the MAIA project's activities and Climate Research Communication Network.

The recent updates and open availability of the core IAMs developed in the project create new opportunities for synergies, with DIAMOND concretely offering novel and enhanced modelling tools to support other research projects' activities and studies.

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1 Plan for meaningful collaborations and synergies

This plan was set out early in the project (as part of milestone report MS4, in July 2023).

1.1 Introduction

DIAMOND is an EU-funded research project under the Horizon Europe framework programme, aimed at updating, upgrading, and fully opening six IAMs that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community, in line with the core idea that boosting cooperation and partnership is key to combatting climate change, and central to the project's scope.

In line with the European Research Area's (ERA) objectives, DIAMOND will enhance the cooperation among universities, business, and other R&I actors, by bringing together experts from different scientific fields in an interdisciplinary approach, and by advancing the transdisciplinary climate-economy modelling co-creation field. Enhanced cooperation in climate policy and research is reflected in four core elements of DIAMOND.

First, through the newly developed models and modules, the project will carry out tailored modelling analyses on long-term strategies of major emitting countries both in the EU and outside. In this direction, the consortium brings together a global consortium of research/modelling teams from 12 countries, including European countries, and major emitters outside the EU such as the US and Canada.

Second, cooperation will be further enhanced through co-development and co-design workshops, to strengthen the modelling development and using process in line with the open science principles, supporting comprehension and trustworthiness of models and their respective results among scientists and policymakers, and ensuring ownership of the resulting models and decarbonisation pathways. Based on this demand-driven approach and deeply rooted within the co-design principle, the project will engage different stakeholder groups—policymakers, climate, and integrated assessment modellers, the broader scientific community, industry representatives, NGOs, the civil society, etc.—in multiple steps of the scientific process. These include the co-creation of the research questions, legitimisation of the implementation process and model development, and optimisation of the communication of project results, with representatives from policy, business, and civil society, allowing to translate the motives, concerns, and actions of decision-makers and citizens over climate action in measurable, quantifiable terms and to demonstrate how they can affect and contribute to the wider climate policy and sustainable development objectives.

Finally, many partners (such as ICCS, ISINNOVA, ETH, UNIBAS, BC3, Imperial) have longstanding experience in complementing modelling research with Social Science & Humanities (SSH) insights and will therefore drive the project's ambition to complement its quantitative evidence with analyses from a wide range of fields. This diversity will help enhance mutual learning among the IAM, SSH, and policy communities to ensure coherence between different tools developed and used to inform climate action, and consistency with the best available and open science.

These elements of the DIAMOND project only reflect the project's conceptual perception of cooperation in the policymaking and research world. Considering the new challenges brought about by climate change, sustainability, disruptions, risks and unknowns, the project acknowledges that successfully reshaping our world in sustainable pathways not only requires cooperative action but also dictates that scientific support and technical capacity to climate policymaking be revolutionised and carried out in an equally cooperative manner as well.

Cooperation in science is also reflected in two other elements of DIAMOND.

The first element lies in the enhancement of an open-access, data exchange platform for modelling information in support of climate action, the I²AM PARIS¹ platform. Our project will notably exploit I²AM PARIS, which was produced in PARIS REINFORCE and used in three other EU-funded projects (H2020 NDC ASPECTS² and ENCLUDE³ and Horizon Europe IAM COMPACT⁴) as a vessel to coordinate modelling and foster knowledge exchange. Its scientific interface has enabled exchanging and harmonising datasets, assumptions, and scenarios to be used in all modelling activities, thereby not only providing a common basis and reference point for all analyses but also making model inter-comparisons more meaningful and targeted at model-inherent features. In the context of DIAMOND, I²AM PARIS will be enhanced in terms of content and features especially within the context of the newly developed IAMs both from the project itself and its sister projects.

The second element traverses the consortium boundaries and constitutes the subject of this report: the project will actively seek to create synergies and establish ties with relevant scientific efforts and research projects in this domain. Synergies can come in many forms and have multiple aims, but given the objectives, scope, and framework of the DIAMOND project, we distinguish two axes of synergies, both aimed at delivering high-quality, relevant, and robust policy prescriptions: (a) joining scientific forces to promote science; and (b) broadening outreach to promote inclusiveness, transdisciplinarity, and stakeholder participation. There are research projects that are offered for establishing synergies in the first axis, projects offered for coordinating efforts in the second axis, and others that can be reached for both types of cooperation. There are also projects that explicitly aim to foster cooperation, and these will also be exploited to expand the space for synergies.

This report presents key elements of coordination and is based on the outcome of a review carried out early in the project, including the analysis of information gathered through internal and informal stakeholder and SAB members' consultations and brainstorming, as well as suggestions from the European Commission and the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), regarding the establishment of synergies among—at least— HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02-03 sister projects.

We distinguish two categories of relevant research projects and initiatives, with which DIAMOND will seek to establish ties for coordination and synergies: (a) projects of the Horizon Europe CL5-2022-D1-02-03 programme, on "Improvement of Integrated Assessment Models in support of climate policies", i.e., sister projects (Section 3); and (b) other projects and initiatives (Section 4).

¹ <https://www.i2am-paris.eu/>

² <https://www.ndc-aspects.eu/>

³ <https://www.encludeproject.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.iam-compact.eu/>

1.2 Purpose, assumptions, and principles

1.2.1 Purpose

The main purpose of this report is to outline the basis for an effective strategy for the coordination and communication elements addressing the following questions:

- How to raise awareness of projects and generate shared interest in looking beyond programme territory, thematic, and partnerships?
- How to ensure that requests for complementarities are a natural feature of projects?
- How to establish coordination and cooperation between projects, the management models, and methodologies of which differ to a significant extent?
- How to turn identified overlaps of project territories and/or themes into an opportunity, and build synergies across projects?
- How to make project participants/consortium members aware of coordination and cooperation possibilities and benefits?
- What tools and means are or would need to be made available to enable coordination and cooperation?
- How to promote and better communicate interrelations between DIAMOND and other project and initiatives (the most notable being the Horizon Europe “CL5-2022-D1-02-03” sister projects)?
- How to better achieve the objectives and maximise impacts through engagement with other initiatives and parties?

In essence, the plan for coordination and synergies is a report on defining mutually agreeable ways, in which the DIAMOND consortium can reach out, agree upon, and then coordinate and synergise project activities with other HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02-03 projects and other relevant interventions financed by the EU, EU Member States or project partner countries. The progress and extent of implementation of this plan will be reflected in project deliverable D6.10 (“Report on synergies with other projects”), due in Month 36.

1.2.2 Overarching assumptions

The Plan for coordination and synergies document has a set of assumptions under which it is elaborated, as a basis to update as other relevant “CL5-2022-D1” projects start:

- Other relevant projects, including our sister projects, have a positive attitude and show willingness to promote greater openness, cooperate, and above all to share their knowledge, experience, and methodologies to be applied in their own projects, and to make themselves available;
- If other projects should elaborate similar coordination and synergy plans, these plans are not substantially different from the present report;
- The contracting authority, CINEA, and in particular the DIAMOND Project Advisor promotes synergies among the projects funded under the same Unit, by sharing information and creating the spaces for collaboration.
- Collaboration is expanded to include non-high-income countries by fostering their capacity, and securing access to data and information symmetry.

1.2.3 Core principles

The overall objective of the partner coordination mechanism is to effectively collaborate, harmonise, and align efforts with that of the EC to help achieve the vision of “enhanced integrated assessment in pursuit of global climate goals”, as laid out by the HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02-03 topic. The principles outlined below should guide

the DIAMOND approach.

1. **Project harmonisation.** Effective project harmonisation is required to support Horizon Europe priorities and, in this context, encourage harmonisation of project instruments and processes among the projects, in addition to aligning specific activities, including but not limited to meetings, reviews, and documentation.
2. **Alignment.** Projects should contribute to scientific progress as well as co-create to national climate action and inform policymaking through integrating inputs from a wide range of stakeholders—representing policy, science, industry, and broader society. Co-creation entails a collaborative process of knowledge production that combines scientific and non-scientific bodies of knowledge and contributes to a holistic understanding. This implies developing joint actions and activities that support the goals, objectives, and outcomes of the projects.
3. **Improved information sharing and learning.** The approach should encourage projects to improve information sharing and build capacities through regular meetings, thematic seminars and workshops, trainings, electronic updates, and other informal dissemination channels.
4. **Enhanced transdisciplinarity.** Projects should foster the contribution of SSH as a cross-cutting issue aimed at improving assessments and response to global climate goals as well as delivering on multiple environmental, economic, and social objectives simultaneously while considering constraints related to feasibility and acceptability.

1.2.4 Lessons learnt as a basis to build synergies

Key to delivering on our work program will be our capacity to build on existing and emerging research projects or activities from modelling consortia. We will leverage the knowledge produced in projects (a) coordinating diverse modelling ensembles and bringing together the research landscape (ECEMF); (b) providing robust, model-based scientific evidence in support of climate policy (e.g., ENGAGE, PARIS REINFORCE, INNOPATHS); (c) expanding model capabilities to address new policy challenges (e.g., NAVIGATE, LOCOMOTION); (d) delving into (cross-) sectoral aspects of Paris-compliant decarbonisation (e.g., NDC ASPECTS, REEEM); (e) developing capacity from global and national perspectives (e.g., COMMIT, CD-Links); (f) touching upon critical aspects of climate action like behavioural change (e.g., CAMPAIGNERS, ENCLUDE, FULFILL); (g) linking diverse models in studying energy transitions (e.g., SENTINEL, openENTRANCE); (h) exploring action at sub-national level (e.g., TIPPING+, Clima-Med, C-Track 50); and (i) fostering dialogue with various stakeholder groups (e.g., DEEDS, EU GCC CEN II).

We will notably exploit the IAM PARIS platform produced in PARIS REINFORCE and used in NDC ASPECTS, ENCLUDE and other projects as a vessel to coordinate modelling. We will also exploit our ties to modelling communities that have been successfully operating for decades, such as the Energy Modeling Forum (EMF) and the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium (IAMC), dedicated to promoting knowledge exchange among modelling groups, with some focusing on open-source tools (e.g., openmod) or capacity building for sustainable development (e.g., OpTIMUS or the UK's Climate Compatible Growth programme), as well as other initiatives like the IEA-ETSAP focussing on targeted aspects of DIAMOND (TIMES-based modelling to support the development of OMNIA). IAMC protocols, templates, repositories, and procedures will be adapted to include the broader set of modelling types available, focusing on inter-comparisons, harmonisation, evaluation, validation, and scenario development. EMF's principles (impartiality, user orientation, disclosure, understanding of policy insights) will guide our quest for policy-relevant, comprehensive, and comprehensible science. We will keep track of the scientific advances and empirical evidence presented in EMP-E; our links with the projects underpinning it will allow us to contribute to its activities. We will finally advance the 'best available science', as reviewed in major scientific assessments, like IPCC's AR6: eleven authors of the AR6 WGIII (mitigation report) are affiliated with the

consortium.

Figure 1 illustrates the project’s links to the existing consortia and processes, as of project kick-off.

Figure 1. Links with existing research projects, consortia, networks, and communities

A basic component of synergising lies in the exploitation of the knowledge and experience produced in the array of previous and/or ongoing relevant research efforts in the climate-economy modelling and climate policy support domains. These have largely formed the foundations of the DIAMOND project novelties, as reflected in its truly co-creative research approach, in the dynamic Policy Response Mechanism, and in the expansion of the modelling comfort zone via emphasising the resilience and robustness of resulting policy prescriptions. These can help drive our efforts to identify both the research projects, with which productive ties could potentially be established, and the types of potential synergies that should be sought.

Table 1 summarises previous projects in this area as well as how DIAMOND has chosen to exploit their knowledge and experience, including the final batch of H2020 projects, under LC-CLA-01-2018, LC-SC3-CC-2-2018, and LC-CLA-10-2020.

Table 1. Reference to previous (H2020) EU-funded research projects that have been implemented in this field

Project	DIAMOND envisaged contributions to advancing knowledge
4I-TRACTION	4I-TRACTION provides transformative policy recommendations for a net-zero EU economy and can inform DIAMOND on 1.5°C compatible pathways.

CAMPAIGNers	DIAMOND can benefit from the lifestyle transformation research conducted in CAMPAIGNers and how citizen-led climate action can tackle climate change.
CDLINKS	CDLINKS has components of leveraging international networks and knowledge sharing and DIAMOND can build upon their existing networks, carrying it out further to acclaim members of this network into the Policy Response Mechanism.
COACH	COACH provided an improved downscaled assessment of the risks and costs of climate change in Europe that can be of direct usability from DIAMOND. IAM COMAPT can also benefit from co-designing principles and integration techniques from COACCH and extend them out to our stakeholders.
C-Track 50	C-Track 50 promoted and strengthened multi-level governance between the EU, national, regional and local levels, through a series of roundtables and bilateral exchanges. As such, it provides DIAMOND with the opportunity to broaden its stakeholder network, in the countries represented in both projects.
ENCLUDE	ENCLUDE focuses on the operationalization of the energy citizenship concept at all scales of policy making for decarbonisation. DIAMOND can be informed on the ways knowledge was co-created and mobilised towards just and inclusive climate action in ENCLUDE.
ENGAGE	DIAMOND can benefit from scenario development and national and global low carbon feasible pathways generated via ENGAGE. ENGAGE intends to develop new pathways in an iterative global and national stakeholder process, ensuring their credibility and legitimacy; these can inform the scenario design process of DIAMOND.
FULFILL	DIAMOND can make use of the sufficiency indicators developed in FULFILL and the metrics about the contribution that lifestyle changes through sufficiency can have to reduce GHG emissions in Europe.
INNOPATHS	DIAMOND can be informed by the treatment of innovation in IAM in INNOPATHS and stakeholder inclusion for scenario development.
LOCOMOTION	LOCOMOTION project develops “WILIAM”, an integrated assessment model that will be used in DIAMOND to study the role of behavioural change and social innovation in the transition drawing from lessons learnt in LC-CLA-10-b projects. The project disseminates its results via multiple interfaces (open-source software with extensive modelling documentation for scientists/modellers, and user-friendly web interface for policymakers and other stakeholders), which can be used in tandem with I ² AM PARIS to promote synergies.
NAVIGATE	NAVIGATE expands model capabilities to better represent social heterogeneity and impacts of lifestyle changes, advancements that can be exploited by DIAMOND modelling suite. IAM NAVIGATOR platform (comprising teaching material, a scenario portal, and a methodological toolbox) can also inform the update of I ² AM PARIS.
NDC ASPECTS	NDC ASPECTS focuses on sectoral systems with limited progress to decarbonisation, and DIAMOND can benefit from the enhanced understanding in terms of transformation dynamics, specific challenges, and policy options across these sectors.
openENTRANCE	The modelling platform created in the context of openENTRANCE provides open a large dataset on the energy transition for each EU country, including data about human behaviour, which can be used in modelling exercises within DIAMOND.

PARIS REINFORCE	DIAMOND will actively exploit and enhance the I ² AM PARIS, an open access, multi-model, data exchange platform created within PARIS REINFORCE project. DIAMOND will build on the harmonised interpretation of regional climate policies created in PARIS REINFORCE to contribute to capacity development for national teams and allow updated representation of previous and current policies/pledges in IAMs. Furthermore, DIAMOND will exploit and expand the diverse network of policy experts and stakeholders in PARIS REINFORCE Stakeholder Council.
REEEM	DIAMOND will build on the REEEM results on renewables and employment as well as the indicators on how decarbonisation pathways can affect specific regions in the EU.
SENTINEL	Potential synergies between DIAMOND and SENTINEL could revolve around modelling documentation, scenario harmonisation and outcome visualisation in the I ² AM PARIS platform and/or the platform developed in SENTINEL.
SENSEI	DIAMOND can benefit from energy efficiency aspects in modelling developed by SENSEI.
TIPPING+	TIPPING+ conducted a systematic and comparative analysis of 20 case studies of European and international Coal and Carbon Intensive Regions (CCIRs) to identify potential Social-Ecological Tipping Points in that region. DIAMOND can leverage this analysis to support clean-energy transitions in these CCIRs.

1.3 Synergies with sister projects

1.3.1 Brief presentation of the projects

The activities outlined in this report have been motivated by the DIAMOND project's commitment to addressing the need for synergies and potential coordination of efforts in the implementation of the IAM- and communication-related research and innovation projects/components of the Horizon Europe "CL5-2021-D1-01: Climate sciences and responses" package, on top of DIAMOND's CL5-2022-D1-02 topic. Therefore, the project is, first and foremost, aiming at boosting fruitful coordination and productive synergies among the following projects:

- Improvement of Integrated Assessment Models in support of climate policies (CL5-2022-D1-02-03)
 - PRISMA** (01/01/2023 – 31/12/2023; 48 months) coordinated by CMCC (16 partners)
 - WorldTrans** (01/12/2022 – 30/11/2026; 48 months) coordinated by MET.NO (10 partners)
- Enhanced integrated assessment in pursuit of global climate goals (CL5-2021-D1-01-04)
 - IAM COMPACT** (01/09/2022 – 31/08/2025; 36 months) coordinated by NTUA (22 partners)
 - ELEVATE** (01/09/2022 – 31/08/2026; 48 months) coordinated by PBL (20 partners)
- Better understanding of the interactions between climate change impacts and risks, mitigation, and adaptation options (CL5-2021-D1-01-05)
 - DISTENDER** (01/06/2022 – 30/11/2025; 42 months) coordinated by UPM (32 partners)
 - KNOWING** (01/06/2022 – 31/05/2026; 48 months) coordinated by AIT (20 partners)
 - NEVERMORE** (01/06/2022 – 31/05/2026; 48 months) coordinated by FBK (16 partners)
- Maximising the impact and synergy of European climate change research and innovation (CL5-2021-D1-01-03)
 - MAGICA** (01/06/2022 – 31/05/2026; 48 months) coordinated by CMCC (24 partners)
 - MAIA** (01/09/2022 – 31/08/2025; 36 months) coordinated by BC3 (14 partners)

Figure 2. DIAMOND “sister” projects (DIAMOND is in white, sister projects where DIAMOND partners are involved are in purple, all others are in black)

The coordination and synergising mechanism is expected to help build on the momentum developed within each of the Horizon Europe “CL5-2021-D1-01” & “CL5-2022-D1-02-03” components, to ensure synergies in the modelling analyses and other scientific activities; and promoting communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, by cultivating a broader stakeholder buy-in as well as shifting from four separate stakeholder networks to a collective one.

1.3.1.1 WorldTrans

The [WorldTrans](#) project will focus on fundamental limitations of advanced IAMs. These include the weak representation of social, human, and economic heterogeneity, the limited representation of feedback between the domains of nature and humans, and the lack of transparency concerning the inner workings of the models and the uptake of results and engagement of citizens and stakeholders. The project will address systemic, structural deficiencies in current IAMs, by applying system dynamics methods and modelling to deal transparently with multi-scale issues and policy response options. Specifically, the project aims to:

- address systemic, structural deficiencies in current IAMs rather than making incremental improvements
- sacrifice details of any particular sector or process, instead capturing the essences of their functions in order to focus on how those processes affect each other within and across domains
- use system dynamics methods and modelling to deal transparently with multiscale issues and policy response options
- “bridge gaps” between models, experts and user communities by developing attractive learning environments that allows for simulations of decision making processes and joint reflections of meaning and implication

WorldTrans is coordinated by Cecilie Mauritzen of the Norwegian Meteorological Institute and started in December 2022. Key aspects of the WorldTrans project that could prove vital for synergies with DIAMOND include: (a) its ambition to build new communities of integrated assessment models (IAM) experts and users (citizens and stakeholders alike), and (b) its focus on IAM transparency and openness.

1.3.1.2 PRISMA

The PRISMA project aims to bring these models to the next level by focusing on four key areas of improvement, namely the representation of distributional justice and efficiency, innovation and finance, climate impacts and land-use implications, and lifestyle change and circularity. In these four key areas the project will improve existing large-scale IAMs and sectorial models and consider the linking of different models where applicable. Specifically, the project aims to:

- embed stakeholder engagement and co-production across the project.
- utilise a large suite of IAMs of different types and scopes to further develop, improve, and apply them for common policy analysis and Net-zero pathway development.
- focus on Europe and current (Fit for 55/European Green Deal) and planned climate and environmental policies.
- improve the spatial and temporal scales of modelling tools and consider in particular societal change in terms of behaviour, structural change in the economy.
- release the developed new modules along with transparent and accessible documentation and use it in capacity building activities.

The PRISMA project is coordinated by Cassinelli Mariaester of the Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC) and started in January 2023. Key aspects of the WorldTrans project that could prove vital for synergies with DIAMOND include the open modelling tools and databases created by the project.

1.3.1.3 ELEVATE

[ELEVATE](#) aims to create a robust scientific understanding required to strengthen NDCs and current climate policies towards reaching net-zero emissions. For this, ELEVATE brings together a unique multidisciplinary consortium of leading international and national modelling teams, climate policy experts and social scientists. It is not only the other project funded under the Horizon Europe “CL5-2021-D1-01” topic, but also the single project sharing the same overall objective of DIAMOND, which is to support the design and assessment of post-2030 climate policies. In particular, it aims to:

- interact directly with policymakers to define information gaps and attractive policies, thereby enhancing the usability of the knowledge base and stimulating mutual learning;
- systematically assess NDCs and policies at the global and national levels to identify current progress and good practice policies;
- explore a range of critical enabling factors related to sectoral action, international climate policy and the relationship with justice and sustainable development that can be leveraged to strengthen action.

Starting in September 2022, ELEVATE is coordinated by Detlef van Vuuren and Isabela Schmidt Tagomori of the Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL). Key aspects of ELEVATE that could prove vital for synergies with DIAMOND include: (a) the participation of University of Maryland in both consortia; and (b) the ELEVATE Research Exchange Programme enabling early and mid-career researchers, from within or outside the consortium, to visit one of the ELEVATE partner institutions and have the opportunity to interact with people from different cultural and educational backgrounds.

1.3.1.4 IAM COMPACT

The [IAM COMPACT](#) project is an EU-funded research project under the Horizon Europe framework programme, aimed at effectively supporting the assessment of global climate goals, progress, and feasibility space, as well as the design of the next round of NDCs and policy planning beyond 2030 for major emitters and non-high-income countries. The project aims to:

- support the assessment of global climate progress, needs, and feasibility, and the preparation of national policies for the post-2030 period, toward mid-century climate neutrality.
- place climate action in a holistic sustainable development framework, working across the broad spectrum of sustainability.
- enhance the robustness of scientific outputs via an interdisciplinary toolbox benchmarking and validating IAM results with sectoral models and coupling modelling with uncertainty analysis tools.
- co-create policy-relevant modelling via an international policy response mechanism.
- establish an integration process that co-produces science and policy prescriptions.
- open the 'black box' of scientific inputs, processes and outputs in line with the principles of open science, ensuring the data used/produced are FAIR.
- engage in the deep/extreme uncertainty space.
- boost international cooperation, partnership, and capacity.

Key aspects of the IAM COMPACT project that could prove vital for synergies with DIAMOND include: (a) the use of two IAMs and one modelling framework that are used in both projects (GCAM, PROMETHEUS, and CLEWs); (b) the shared use and expansion of the I²AM PARIS platform; (c) the participation of Basque Centre for Climate Change (BC3), Center for International Climate Research (CICERO), and Imperial College of Science, technology and Medicine (Imperial); and, critically, (d) its coordination by the National Technical university of Athens (NTUA), a sister institute of ICCS (coordinating DIAMOND).

1.3.1.5 DISTENDER

DISTENDER will provide integrated strategies by building a methodological framework that guide the integration of climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies through participatory approaches in ways that respond to the impacts and risks of climate change, supported by quantitative and qualitative analysis that facilitates the understanding of interactions, synergies, and trade-offs. Holistic approaches to mitigation and adaptation must be tailored to the context-specific situation and this requires a flexible and participatory planning process to ensure legitimate and salient action, carried out by all important stakeholders. The project aims to develop:

- a set of multi-driver qualitative and quantitative socio-economic-climate scenarios through a facilitated participatory process that integrates bottom-up knowledge and locally relevant drivers with top-down information from the global European Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) and downscaled Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) from IPCC.
- a cross-sectorial and multi-scale impact assessment modelling toolkit to analyse the complex interactions over multiple sectors, including an economic evaluation framework
- a Decision Support System (DSS) which will include guidelines, manuals, easy-to-use tools and experiences from the application of the cases studies.

The DISTENDER project is coordinated by Roberto San José of Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) and

started in June 2022. Key aspects of the DISTENDER project that could prove vital for synergies with DIAMOND include: (a) its participatory approaches through networks to promote and exchange the outputs of the project (b) its localised climate storylines through a downscaling framework that could inform analyses within DIAMOND.

1.3.1.6 KNOWING

KNOWING aims at developing a modelling framework to help understand and quantify the interactions between the impacts and risks of climate change, mitigation pathways and adaptation strategies. The framework will be used to assess the advancing climate science and further broadening and deepening the knowledge base is essential to inform the societal transition towards a climate-neutral and climate-resilient society by 2050, as well as towards a more ambitious greenhouse gas reduction target by 2030. The project develops knowledge and solutions that will help:

- authorities to know which measures and conditions for adaptation to set along climate mitigation pathways.
- businesses, production and service providers to know how to adapt to changing conditions and climate impacts.
- people to know how to adapt their lifestyles in the most sufficient way and why measures need to be set.

The project is coordinated by Alexandra Millonig of the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) and started in June 2022. A key aspect of the project that could prove vital for synergies with DIAMOND is its Impact Interaction Knowledge Base comprising causal relations of climate and intervention impacts, rebound effects, and coping strategies, to inform the scientific community.

1.3.1.7 NEVERMORE

The NEVERMORE project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme, aims to develop integrated models and tools for simulating and assessing the impacts and risks of climate change, as well as to realise new interactive digital tools useful for citizens and policy-makers to learn about future scenarios and to make mitigation and adaptation policies more effective. Within this scenario, Stakeholder Councils at the local and transnational levels are established to ensure the active involvement of public and private actors in the co-design, co-creation and co-assessment of activities based on social innovation. The NEVERMORE approach:

- integrates information from physical modelling of impacts and risk analysis methodologies and aligns them across different scales: from national, EU and global scales (in the IAM) to local and regional scales via five case studies
- is embedded in a practical and user-friendly ICT toolkit, including decision-making tools, designed and developed with and for different stakeholders and end-users involved throughout the project via five Local and a Transnational Council of Stakeholders, by leveraging social innovation frameworks, participatory processes and co-design techniques.

The project is coordinated by Alessia Torre of Bruno Kessler Foundation, Trento, Italy and started in June 2026. Key aspects of the NEVERMORE project that could prove vital for synergies with DIAMOND include: (a) its Stakeholder Council at the local (including Sitia island in Greece) and Transnational level, and (b) the participation of DIAMOND's project manager (Alexandros Nikas) in the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) of NEVERMORE.

1.3.1.8 MAGICA

The MAGICA project will maximise the synergies between infrastructure investments and initiatives of climate

change research and innovation (R&I) across the European Research Area (ERA) by building upon and further implementing the Mission of JPI Climate in support of the international and European climate agenda. The creation of a Joint Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda on climate change for ERA 2025-2034, a regular forum with the European Ministries of Research and Climate along with other funding bodies, as well as a multi-directional dialogue with different relevant social actors, will accelerate the development and exchange of knowledge from R&I. MAGICA will inform and support policy-making and climate actions, based on iterative interactions among the strategic, scientific and societal components of climate change R&I. The project aims to:

- maximize the synergies between infrastructure investments and initiatives of climate change research and innovation across the European Research Area (ERA) by building upon and further implementing the Mission of JPI Climate in support of the international and European climate agenda (including the European Green Deal and Adaptation Strategy).
- accelerate the development, provision and exchange of knowledge from research and innovation to inform and support policy-making and climate actions. It will do this via improved coordination of ongoing and future climate initiatives at transnational, national, regional and municipal levels and more efficient use of resources.

The project is coordinated by Giulia Galluccio of Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC) and started in June 2022. A key aspect of the project that could prove vital for synergies with DIAMOND is its scientific arena, created to enhance the debate and discussion within the scientific community on climate R&I priorities, and will be synthesised in a Joint Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda on climate change for ERA 2025-2034.

1.3.1.9 MAIA

The [MAIA](#) project aims to provide and implement a set of effective measures that facilitate a wider dissemination, communications, and interconnection of completed and ongoing EU climate change research projects. In particular, MAIA will enhance:

- the connectivity of existing communities (consolidation and activation of a Pan-European community of problem owners, solution providers, and enablers);
- the connectivity of knowledge and technological infrastructure (creation of the MAIA Portal); and
- the connectivity of the EU climate research (coordinating an EU climate change research Cluster).

The project is being coordinated by the Basque Centre for Climate Change (BC3). Key elements of MAIA that make it idea to help foster synergies with the broader scientific landscape revolve around its mission to reinforce communication and dissemination activities of EU climate change research projects, amplifying them by an active outreach campaign, aiming towards the democratisation of climate knowledge, as well as to develop a comprehensive cross-project exploitation-support programme, while addressing awareness raising, strengthening the science-policy and science-civil society interfaces, and supporting climate action and sustainable behaviours through several actions dealing with active dialogue.

1.3.2 Spaces for coordination and synergies

1.3.2.1 Coordination of research activities

The project manager of sister project WorldTrans (Cecilie Mauritzen) has agreed to participate in the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) of DIAMOND while the project manager of DIAMOND (Alexandros Nikas) participates in the

SAB of WorldTrans. The rationale is that participating in the steering committees of sister projects can be beneficial for the research activities and outcomes of the projects, as it encourages projects to directly exploit one another's results as well as to cover emerging knowledge/research gaps and unfold their activities in a complementary manner. Bilateral contacts with the project management team of PRISMA have already been established.

1.3.2.2 Geographical and thematic complementarities

DIAMOND will investigate complementarities with its projects, in terms of the modelling analyses envisaged. This includes coordination of national and regional analyses, in order to avoid duplicate research of specific aspects, policies, sectors, dimensions, etc. for countries/regions that will be analysed by both DIAMOND and at least one of the other projects.

1.3.2.3 Open access to the modelling platforms

A key objective of the DIAMOND project is to open the 'black box' of scientific inputs, processes, and outputs, by providing open access to the data and code produced, transparently mapping outputs onto assumptions, and exploiting/expanding the I²AM PARIS open exchange platform with open databases, briefs, papers, and policy support toolboxes for each exercise, leading to the first open and large-scale library of applications based on IAM outcomes. The platform is already used by other currently ongoing H2020 projects (ENCLUDE, NDC ASPECTS) and will be further expanded in the context of the Horizon Europe project IAM COMPACT. This encourages exploitation of the platform for the model documentation, scenario harmonisation and outcome visualisation of other research activities, and reflects the initial intention for the platform to evolve into a vessel for knowledge exchange for the wider modelling community and an authoritative source of modelling information for stakeholders. The same can be pursued for the project's research activities in other platforms out there (including but not limited to the IAMC). This not only enhances the outreach of each project, but also traverses the project boundaries, by allowing for sharing common scenario frameworks among all projects as well as carrying out model inter-comparisons for countries/regions/the globe, where modelling analysis will be performed by several projects.

1.3.2.4 A stakeholder inter-network

Key objectives aside, albeit to a different extent, all sister projects highlight stakeholder engagement. Although the idea of stakeholder representation is to make sure that all stakeholder groups are adequately involved in the process, there is only so many people a project can have ties with or reach out to. DIAMOND will, therefore, investigate the possibility of joining forces with other projects to develop one large, cross-project stakeholder inter-network, acknowledging of course the limitations posed by the ethics requirements of each project and the European Commission.

1.3.2.5 Joint communication, dissemination and exploitation activities

Joint academic publications

One of the DIAMOND priorities is to foster sharing of knowledge and research results among peers and other potential users. The sister projects could join forces and disseminate results in joint papers, or actively organise co-editing and/or submitting to joint special issues.

Moreover, DIAMOND aims to communicate directly with the sister projects and other relevant projects to further raise their interest and highlight the joint benefit from submission of manuscripts for publication. In this effort, DIAMOND presents a significant advantage—as a model development project it can, and so has so far managed to achieve this, offer the models updated and expanded within the framing of the project to other efforts in the communities of the practice of each tool, ensuring long-lasting impact.

Joint policy publications

Later in the project lifetime, DIAMOND will explore the possibility for synergies regarding the publication of policy briefs on topics such as (i) future action pledges and long-term decarbonisation pathways of the EU and of other major emitting and non-high-income countries, (ii) sectoral decarbonisation pathways such as on decarbonising international transport and bunker fuels, and transforming global steel sector (iii) co-impacts and trade-offs in the broader EU policy framework, (iv) interactions between EU climate policy agenda and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, (v) county-level analyses of transformation drivers, challenges, and policy options in key sectors to provide concrete recommendations for strengthening climate policies and (vi) lessons to inform and contribute to the upcoming global stocktake. One possibility to be explored is the production of a bigger joint publication encompassing the results of the modelling runs and results of all sister projects.

Joint policy events

DIAMOND plans to engage beneficiaries of similar projects to the policy events, the aims of which include co-creation of research and co-development of models with stakeholders. In parallel, DIAMOND partners will seek participation in policy events of other projects. Researchers from other projects will be invited to join multi-layered stakeholder engagement process and therefore be the first to be invited to the policy events of the project, i.e., policy steering and capacity development workshops and the final conference.

Stakeholder engagement is a core part of DIAMOND and revolves around co-design process, a process that will facilitate constructive dialogue and knowledge sharing between stakeholders and modellers with the aim of generating policy-relevant models and insights from the DIAMOND research agenda. The core objectives of stakeholder engagement within DIAMOND are:

- To achieve successful and ambitious science co-creation through the inclusion of non-scientists in the modelling process—including model development.
- To ensure policy relevance of research activity through the structured involvement of stakeholders.
- To facilitate knowledge exchange among scientists, policymakers, business, and civil society actors.

Capacity development activities

A key pillar of DIAMOND is to employ the new models and carry out capacity development activities and create ownership of the science-based policy support process, especially those models dedicated to this purpose such as CLEWs and the CLEWs-EU derivative of the project, which will be central in the workshops and training activities organised. These activities aimed at enhancing modelling capacity and creating new tools for policy and decision support will be made fully open in the platform and project website.

Joint communication activities

DIAMOND plans to foster collaboration with other projects by:

- Following the other projects' social media accounts
- Inviting other projects (and project consortium members) to follow the DIAMOND social media accounts
- Examining the possibility for joint press releases and articles
- Examining the possibility for specific joint social media campaigns to improve the visibility of the results of the projects
- Inviting other projects to have a specific session in DIAMOND workshops and final conference
- Requesting from other projects a specific session in their conferences/workshops and other public events
- Investigating the possibility for a joint public event
- Publishing articles, publications, and news on the websites of other projects and publishing news about

and research outputs of other projects on the DIAMOND website

- Investigating the possibility for joint participation in other meetings and events, possibly upon suggestion of the Project Advisor, to promote the visibility and outputs of the projects.

1.4 A map of other projects and initiatives for consideration

This section refers to projects and initiatives to be considered for synergies and coordination, outside the spectrum of the CL5-2021-D1-02 programme. This includes research projects and efforts that provide the space for joining scientific forces to promote science and/or broadening outreach to promote inclusiveness and stakeholder participation, whether DIAMOND consortium members participate in these efforts or not.

Table 2. Tentative (not exhaustive) list of Horizon Europe and H2020 projects to be considered for synergies

Project (abbr.)	Full name	Website	Duration	Consortium leader	Focus/scope	Potential joint action(s)
4C	Climate-Carbon Interactions in the Current Century	https://4c-carbon.eu/	06/2019 – 11/2023	University of Exeter, UK	New more accurate models of how carbon affects climate change	Data on carbon emissions and climate projections
4I-TRACTION	Innovation, Investment, Infrastructure and sector Integration: TRAnsformative policies for a ClimaTe-neutral European Union	https://www.4i-traction.eu/	06/2021 – 05/2024	Ecologic Institute. Germany	Taking stock of the current mix of EU climate policies	Transformative innovative pathways and policy avenues.
CINTRAN	Carbon Intensive Regions in Transition - Unravelling the Challenges of Structural Change	https://coaltransitions.org/projects/cintran/	05/2020 – 04/2024	WI, Germany	Studying the dynamics of decarbonisation	Regional level insights and recommendations
CircEular	Developing circular pathways for a EU low-carbon transition	https://circ-eular.org/	09/2022 – 08/2026	IIASA, Asutria	CircEular will develop new modelling approaches for analysing circularity from a systems perspective	Share of data and of economy-wide material stocks and flows, GHG emissions, and industrial value chains in mobility and buildings
CircoMod	Circular Economy Modelling for Climate Change Mitigation	https://circomod.eu/	06/2022 – 05/2026	University of Utrecht, Netherlands	CIRCUMOD will develop a new generation of advanced models and scenarios that will assess how CE can reduce future GHGs and material use	Share of database (Data Hubs) on circular economy

Project (abbr.)	Full name	Website	Duration	Consortium leader	Focus/scope	Potential joint action(s)
CO2NSTRUCT	CO2NSTRUCT: Modelling the role of circular economy construction value chains for a carbon-neutral Europe	https://co2nstruct.dtu.dk/	06/2022 – 05/2026	Technical University of Denmark, Denmark	CO2NSTRUCT will delineate a “circular climate mitigation” framework to augment TIMES models focusing on specific carbon-intensive construction materials.	Share of module improvements from TIMES to OMNIA and vice versa.
CONSTRAIN	Constraining uncertainty of multi decadal climate projections	https://constrain-eu.org/	07/2019 – 06/2023	University of Leeds, UK	Making multi-decadal climate change predictions	Data for Carbon Budget; online tools for climate emulation
ECEMF	European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum	https://www.ecemf.eu/	05/2021 – 04/2025	KTH, Sweden	Launch of the European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum, a focal point for European climate and energy policymakers and researchers.	Participation in the forum; conference as part of ECEMF event for policy steering interactions.
ENGAGE	Exploring National and Global Actions to reduce Greenhouse gas Emissions	http://www.engage-climate.org/	09/2019 – 08/2023	IIASA, Austria	New models to carve decarbonisation pathways	Scenario explorer and open-source tools on pathways feasibility; participation in seminars.
ESM2025	Earth system models for the future	https://www.esm2025.eu/	06/2021 – 05/2025	Météo-France, France	Earth system modelling and climate research in support of the Paris Agreement	Open source data and codes; linking framework with IAMs
GENIE	GeoEngineering and Negative Emissions pathways in Europe	https://genie-erc.github.io/	05/2021 – 04/2027	Aarhus, Denmark	Sociotechnical pathways for a zero-emissions future	Dimensions of GHG removal and solar radiation management
GoNEXUS	Innovative tools and solutions for governing the water-energy-food-ecosystems NEXUS under global change	https://gonexus.eu/	06/2021 – 05/2025	UPV, Spain	Tools and solutions to jointly address water, energy, food, and ecosystem challenges	Nexus research-improved policy support
LOCOMOTION	Low-carbon society: an enhanced modelling tool for	https://www.locomotion-2020.eu/	06/2019 – 11/2023	Uva, Spain	A comprehensive, integrated tool for sustainability modelling	User-friendly applications and open-source tools.

Project (abbr.)	Full name	Website	Duration	Consortium leader	Focus/scope	Potential joint action(s)
	the transition to sustainability					
NAVIGATE	Next generation of AdVanced InteGrated Assessment modelling to support climaTE policy making	https://www.navigate-h2020.eu/	09/2019 – 08/2023	PIK, Germany	Improved models for informing and evaluating climate policies	Treatment of transformative structural and technological change in IAMs; datasets, modules, and tools developed (diagnostics, scenario analysis); participation in seminars
NDC ASPECTS	Assessing Sectoral Perspectives on Climate Transitions to support the Global Stocktake and subsequent NDCs	https://ndc-aspects.eu/	05/2021 – 04/2024	WI, Germany	Climate change mitigation - nationally determined contributions for the post 2030 period	Joint events; Enhancement of I ² AM PARIS platform.
PARIS REINFORCE	Delivering on the Paris Agreement: A demand-driven, integrated assessment modelling approach	https://paris-reinforce.eu/	07/2019 – 11/2022	National Technical University of Athens, Greece	A framework to reinforce the science-policy interface of the Paris Agreement.	Modelling inputs; stakeholder engagement; I ² AM PARIS platform
PathFinder	Towards an Integrated Consistent European LULUCF Monitoring and Policy Pathway Assessment Framework	https://www.nibio.no/en/projects/pathfinder	09/2022 – 08/2026	NIBIO, Norway	Why forest monitoring matters	Data maps and forest attributes for Europe

1.5 Action Plan for synergies

The following actions have been and will be implemented by the DIAMOND consortium to create the space for cooperation mentioned in Section 4 above, as illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3. DIAMOND Action Plan for cooperation and synergies

Task	Description	Responsible(s)	Timing
Mapping the relevant projects	Numerous projects have already been identified (Sections 3 and 4). All consortium members will screen other projects that their organisation participates in, in order to assess whether they have	ICCS and all partners	May 2023 to October 2023 (completed)

	<p>common grounds with DIAMOND to be considered for synergies.</p> <p>The screening will be performed primarily over the internet and personal bilateral discussions. The result of the mapping will be reflected in Tables 2 and 3, which will be enriched.</p>		
Initiating contact with projects	<p>An initial assessment of the potential for synergies will be performed once the list of projects is ready. This exercise will reveal which of the listed project is relevant to be contacted directly for further investigation of the potential and above all of the willingness to coordinate their efforts with DIAMOND. This direct contact is necessary for building trust between projects. Once trust and common understanding have been established, the interested projects are expected to share the timeframe of their key tasks, deliverables, and milestones to enable DIAMOND to identify the space for synergies and coordination.</p>	ICCS	November 2023 – January 2024 <i>(completed)</i>
Establishing synergies	<p>Actions such as the ones described in Sections 3 and 4 will be implemented with the CL5-2021-D1-02-03 sister project as well as other relevant projects.</p>	ICCS and all partners	February 2024 – November 2026 <i>(ongoing)</i>
Reporting on the synergies	<p>The progress and extent of implementation of this plan will be reflected in project deliverable D6.10 "Report on collaboration and synergies".</p>	ICCS	November 2025 <i>(this report)</i>

2 Report on synergies achieved as of November 2025

2.1 Joint scientific publications

DIAMOND has already pursued such joint scientific dissemination options. 35 out of a total of 39 scientific publications produced within the project have in fact been published jointly with EU-funded/other projects:

1. Sampedro, J., Rodés-Bachs, C., Smith, S. J., Tomás, M., Urrutia, I., & Van de Ven, D. J. (2025). rhap: A tool to analyze health impacts attributable to household air pollution. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 10(114), 8091. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.08091> (Synergy: GRAPHICS, IAM COMPACT)
2. Rodés-Bachs, C., Sampedro, J., Amich, M., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Belis, C. A., & Van de Ven, D. J. A Socioeconomic Assessment of Projected Health Impacts from Outdoor Air Pollution under Current European Climate Policy. Available at SSRN 5597772. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5597772> (preprint under review) (Synergy: GRAPHICS)
3. Keppo, I. J., Al Khourdajie, A., Gardumi, F., Holtz, G., Nikas, A., Xexakis, G., ... & van de Ven, D.-J., & Zamanipour, B. (2025). Model linking for low-carbon transitions: Technical and conceptual challenges and best practices. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 226 Part C(116384). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.116384> (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, ENTICE, EU-CHINA BRIDGE, ENTICE)
4. van de Ven, D. J., Rodés-Bachs, C., Rouhette, T., Horowitz, R., Sampedro, J., Nikas, A., ... & Koasidis, K. (2025). Beyond “Least-Cost” allocation: Optimising sectoral contributions for Paris-compatible mitigation targets over multiple SDG trade-offs. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-7466126/v1> (preprint under review) (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, NDC ASPECTS)
5. Nikas, A., Frilingou, N., van de Ven, D. J., Sampedro, J., Horowitz, R., Rodés-Bachs, C., ... & Bertram, C. (2025). Regional impacts of energy technologies’ cost of capital on decarbonisation. (preprint under review) (Synergy: IAM COMPACT)
6. Frilingou, N., Van de Ven, D. J., Sampedro, J., Torné, A., Trutnevyte, E., Horowitz, R., ... & Nikas, A. (2025). Cost-optimal vs. policy-driven scenarios for a decarbonised European energy system. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-7847096/v1> (preprint under review) (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, ACCLIMATE, PRISMA)
7. Sognaes, I., & Peters, G. P. (2025). Influence of individual models and studies on quantitative mitigation findings in the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report. *Nature Communications*, 16(1), 8343. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-64091-w> (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, Norwegian Research Council project TRIFECTA)
8. Sampedro, J., Van de Ven, D. J., Horowitz, R., Rodés-Bachs, C., Roman, M. V., Tomas, M., ... & Arto, I. (2025). Enhancing energy and food access through reduction of income inequality does not jeopardize the achievement of existing climate pledges. *Environmental Research Letters*, 20, 114086. <http://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ae17db> (Synergy: GRAPHICS, IAM COMPACT)
9. Lamboll, R., Al Khourdajie, A., & Pelz, S. (2025). How stocks judge COPs: market impacts of climate conferences. *Environmental Research Letters*, 20, 114082. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ae15a6> (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, ELEVATE)
10. Rodés-Bachs, C., Sampedro, J., Frilingou, N., Gardumi, F., & Giudice, C. L. (2025). Open Science Practices in Integrated Assessment Models. *Open Research Europe*, 5, 12. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18824.2> (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, GRAPHICS)

11. Buck, H. J., Al Khourdajie, A., Asayama, S., & Geden, O. (2025). Four scenarios for an IPCC navigating Artificial Intelligence. Research Division EU/Europe, Working Paper Nr. 08/2025, September 2025. https://www.swp-berlin.org/publications/products/arbeitspapiere/WP_Geden_etal_IPCC_290925.pdf (working paper) (Synergy: IAM COMPACT)
12. Sampedro, J., Horowitz, R., Rodés-Bachs, C., Koasidis, K. & Van de Ven, D. J. (2025). GCAM-Europe v7. 2.0: Enhancing Policy-Relevant Climate Modelling Through Spatial and Sectoral Detail. EGU sphere, 2025, 1-32. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-3546> (preprint under review) (Synergy: GRAPHICS)
13. Al Khourdajie, A., Gambhir, A., Keppo, I., Frilingou, N., Mittal, S., van de Ven, D. J., ... & Nikas, A. (2025). Navigating the unexpected: The impact of disruptive events on mitigation scenarios. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-7427967/v1> (preprint under review) (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, WorldTrans, ENTICE, TRANSCIENCE, SPARCCLC, Grant under the National Research Foundation of Korea).
14. Engel, L., Kukowski, C. A., & Hahnel, U. J. (2025). Empowering change: A self-control perspective on how choice architecture interventions can promote sustainable behavior change. *Motivation Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/mot0000396> (Synergy: Grants under the Swiss National Science Foundation)
15. Al Khourdajie, A. (2025). The role of artificial intelligence in climate change scientific assessments. *PLOS Climate*, 4(9), e0000706. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000706> (Synergy: IAM COMPACT)
16. Koasidis, K., Soursoos, A., Xexakis, G., Labella, Á., Karamaneas, A., & Nikas, A. (2025). APOLLO-Live: A multi-criteria-based webtool for synchronous group decision making and consensus support in energy and climate policy deliberations. *Open Research Europe*, 5(88), 88. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19614.3> (Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE, JUSTEM)
17. Zisarou, E., Fragkos, P., Van De Ven, D. J., Mittal, S., Frilingou, N., Rodés-Bachs, C., ... & Nikas, A. (2025). A window of (missed) opportunity? A comprehensive stocktake and energy-system impact assessment of global COVID-19 recovery packages. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 127, 104216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2025.104216> (Synergy: IAM COMPACT)
18. Sandstad, M., Steinert, N. J., Baur, S., & Sanderson, B. M. (2025). METEORv1. 0.1: A novel framework for emulating multi-timescale regional climate responses. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 18(21), 8269-8312. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-18-8269-2025> (Synergy: PROVIDE)
19. van de Ven, D. J., Mittal, S., Nikas, A., Xexakis, G., Gambhir, A., Hermwille, L., ... & Peters, G. P. (2025). Energy and socioeconomic system transformation through a decade of IPCC-assessed scenarios. *Nature Climate Change*, 15(2), 218-226. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41558-024-02198-6> (Synergy: NDC ASPECTS, IAM COMPACT)
20. Pye, S., Bradshaw, M., Price, J., Zhang, D., Kuzemko, C., Sharples, J., ... & Dodds, P. E. (2025). The global implications of a Russian gas pivot to Asia. *Nature Communications*, 16(1), 386. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-55697-7> (Synergy: UK Energy Research Centre Phase 4, FCDO-funded Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) Programme)
21. Beath, H., Mittal, S., Lamboll, R., & Rogelj, J. (2025). An exploration and evaluation framework for climate change mitigation scenarios with varying feasibility and desirability. *Environmental Research Letters*. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/addd35> (Synergy: Hitachi-Imperial Centre for Decarbonisation and Natural Climate Solutions)
22. Calcaterra, M., Aleluia Reis, L., Fragkos, P., Briera, T., de Boer, H. S., Egli, F., ... & Tavoni, M. (2024). Reducing the cost of capital to finance the energy transition in developing countries. *Nature Energy*, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-024-01606-7> (Synergy: PRISMA, ELEVATE, INNOPATHS, ECEMF, IAM)

COMPACT)

23. Nikas, A. (2024). Projecting progress in sustainable development goals vis-à-vis climate action in climate-economy models. *PLOS Clim* 3(7): e0000449. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000449> (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, TRANSCIENCE)
24. Sampedro, J., Van de Ven, D. J., Horowitz, R., Rodés-Bachs, C., Frilingou, N., Nikas, A., ... & Yarlagadda, B. (2024). Energy system analysis of cutting off Russian gas supply to the European Union. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 54, 101450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2024.101450> (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, TRANSCIENCE, GRAPHICS)
25. Joshi, S., Zakeri, B., Mittal, S. *et al.* Global high-resolution growth projections dataset for rooftop area consistent with the shared socioeconomic pathways, 2020–2050. *Sci Data* **11**, 563 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03378-x> (Synergy: CircEular, Grants from the Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC))
26. Moreno, J., Campagnolo, L., Boitier, B., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Gambhir, A., Gonzalez-Eguino, M., Perdana, S., Van de Ven, D.-J., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzi, E., Doukas, H., Gargiulo, M., Herbst, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Neuner, F., Le Mouël, P., & Vielle, M. (2024). The impacts of decarbonization pathways on Sustainable Development Goals in the European Union. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 5(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01309-7> (Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE, IAM COMPACT)
27. McGookin, C., Süsler, D., Xexakis, G., Trutnevyte, E., McDowall, W., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Few, S., Andersen, P. D., Demski, C., Fortes, P., Simoes, S. G., Bishop, C., Rogan, F., & Ó Gallachóir, B. (2024). Advancing participatory energy systems modelling. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 52, 101319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2024.101319> (Synergy: ENCLUDE, JUSTEM, PARIS REINFORCE, IAM COMPACT, CEECIND)
28. Nikas, A., Frilingou, N., Heussaff, C., Fragkos, P., Mittal, S., Sampedro, J., Giarola, S., Sasse, J.-P., Rinaldi, L., Doukas, H., Gambhir, A., Giannousakis, A., Golinucci, N., Koasidis, K., Rocco, M. V., Trutnevyte, E., Xexakis, G., Zachmann, G., Zisarou, E., ... Van de Ven, D.-J. (2024). Three different directions in which the European Union could replace Russian natural gas. *Energy*, 130254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.130254> (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, NDC ASPECTS, MANET)
29. Boitier, B., Nikas, A., Gambhir, A., Koasidis, K., Elia, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Campagnolo, L., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzi, E., Doukas, H., Fougeyrollas, A., Gargiulo, M., Mouël, P. L., Neuner, F., Perdana, S., Ven, D.-J. van de Ven, Vielle, M., Zagamé, P., & Mittal, S. (2023). A multi-model analysis of the EU's path to net zero. *Joule*, 7(12). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2023.11.002> (Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE, IAM COMPACT)
30. Koutsandreas, D., Trachanas, G. P., Pappis, I., Nikas, A., Doukas, H., & Psarras, J. (2023). A multicriteria modeling approach for evaluating power generation scenarios under uncertainty: The case of green hydrogen in Greece. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 50, 101233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2023.101233> (Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE, IAM COMPACT)
31. Bailie, A., Pied, M., Vaillancourt, K., Bahn, O., Koasidis, K., Gambhir, A., Wachsmuth, J., Warnke, P., McWilliams, B., Doukas, H., & Nikas, A. (2023). Co-creating Canada's path to net-zero: A stakeholder-driven modelling analysis. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition*, 4, 100061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rset.2023.100061> (Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE)
32. Koutsellis, T., Xexakis, G., Koasidis, K., Frilingou, N., Karamaneas, A., Nikas, A., & Doukas, H. (2023). In-Cognitive: A web-based Python application for fuzzy cognitive map design, simulation, and uncertainty analysis based on the Monte Carlo method. *SoftwareX*, 23, 101513.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2023.101513> (Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE)

33. Gambhir, A., & Nikas, A. (2023). Seven key principles for assessing emerging low-carbon technological opportunities for climate change mitigation action. *PLOS Climate*, 2(7), e0000235. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000235> (Synergy: IAM COMPACT)
34. Perdana, S., & Vielle, M. (2023). Carbon border adjustment mechanism in the transition to net-zero emissions: Collective implementation and distributional impacts. *Environmental Economics and Policy Studies*, 25(3), 299–329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10018-023-00361-5> (Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE)
35. Cassetti, G., Elia, A., Gargiulo, M., & Chiodi, A. (2023). Reinforcing the Paris Agreement: Ambitious scenarios for the decarbonisation of the Central Asian and Caspian region. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition*, 3, 100048. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rset.2023.100048> (Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE)

2.2 Synergistic presentations at conferences

The following presentations/posters/sessions at conferences also feature material produced through synergies with other projects:

1. Xexakis, G., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Frilingou, N., Sarmas, E., Marinakis, V., Doukas, H. "Cities at the forefront: current modelling practices and opportunities for integrated assessment models—insights from Athens, Greece". 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. [presentation] (Synergy: ACHIEVE)
2. Frilingou, N., Van de Ven, D., Sampedro, J., Horowitz, R., Rodés-Bachs, C., Mittal, S., Torne, A., Trutnevyte, E., Koasidis, K., Nikas, A. (2025). Comparing cost-optimal to policy-driven scenarios for a decarbonised European energy system, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. [presentation] (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, ACCLIMATE, PRISMA)
3. Rodés-Bachs, C., et. al., Health impacts and socioeconomic inequalities of future outdoor air pollution in Europe, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [presentation] (Synergy: GRAPHICS)
4. Rouhette, T., et. al., Towards fire-resilient mitigation pathways in the AFOLU sector: modelling burned area and fire emission feedbacks in integrated assessment models, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [presentation] (Synergy: NDC ASPECTS, CLEVER)
5. Van de Ven, D-J., et. al., GCAM-Europe: Enhancing Policy-Relevant Climate Modelling Through Spatial and Sectoral Detail, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [poster] (Synergy: GRAPHICS)
6. Rodés-Bachs, C., et. al., Open Science Practices in Integrated Assessment Models, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [poster] (Synergy: IAM COMPACT, GRAPHICS)
7. Sampedro, J., et. al., rhap: A tool to analyze health impacts attributable to household air pollution, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [poster] (Synergy: GRAPHICS, IAM COMPACT)
8. Sampedro, J., et. al., Evaluating inter- and intra-regional air pollution inequalities in a decarbonized world, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [poster] (Synergy: GRAPHICS)
9. Frilingou, N., Van de Ven, D-J., Sampedro, J., Horowitz, R., Rodés-Bachs, C., Mittal, S., Torne, A., Trutnevyte, E., Koasidis, K., Nikas, A. "Comparing cost-optimal to policy-driven scenarios for a decarbonised European

- energy system". European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum (ECEMP), October 16 – 17, 2025, Brussels, Belgium. [presentation] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT, ACCLIMATE, PRISMA](#))
10. Xexakis, G., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Frilingou, N., Sarmas, E., Marinakis, V., Doukas, H. "Cities at the forefront: current modelling practices and opportunities for integrated assessment models—insights from Athens, Greece". European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum (ECEMP), October 16 – 17, 2025, Brussels, Belgium. [presentation] ([Synergy: ACHIEVE](#))
 11. Nikas, A., Van de Ven, D.-J., Rodes-Bachs, C., Rouhette, T., Horowitz, R., Sampedro, J., Frilingou, N., Georgiou, K., Zhao, X., Chaudhary, A., Koasidis, K. "Optimising sectoral climate mitigation efforts against multiple sustainability indicators: a multi-objective integrated assessment", 34th European Conference on Operational Research (EURO), July 22-25, 2025, Leeds, United Kingdom. [presentation] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT, NDC ASPECTS](#))
 12. Koasidis, K., Soursos, A., Xexakis, G., Karamaneas, A., & Nikas, A. "A multi-criteria group decision making and consensus reaching webtool for synchronous deliberations using 2-tuple TOPSIS", 34th European Conference on Operational Research (EURO), July 22-25, 2025, Leeds, United Kingdom. [presentation] ([Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE, JUSTEM](#))
 13. Frilingou, N. et al. Regional impacts of energy technologies' cost of capital on decarbonisation. 30th Annual Conference of the European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists, 16 - 19 June 2025, Bergen, Norway. [presentation] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT](#))
 14. Koasidis, K., Soursos, A., Xexakis, G., Karamaneas, A., & Nikas, A. "Enhancing Stakeholder Engagement for a Just Transition: An Operational Research Approach to Participatory Decision-Making", Fifth Swiss Social Sciences and Humanities Energy Research Workshop (SSH Energy), June 16-17, 2025, Zurich, Switzerland. [presentation] ([Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE, JUSTEM](#))
 15. Frilingou, N., Heussaff, C., Zachmann, G., Mittal, S., van de Ven, D., -J., Horowitz, R., ... Koasidis, K., Nikas, A. "Advancing participatory integrated assessment modelling via a Policy Response Mechanism: a novel approach to policy-relevant, stakeholder-driven modelling", Fifth Swiss Social Sciences and Humanities Energy Research Workshop (SSH Energy), June 16-17, 2025, Zurich, Switzerland. [presentation] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT](#))
 16. Tigka, C., Koasidis, K., Ruß, M., Hermwille, L., Rizos, V., Righetti, E., ... & Nikas, A. "Stakeholder insights and socio-technical perspectives for analysing sustainable transitions in energy-intensive industrial regions", Fifth Swiss Social Sciences and Humanities Energy Research Workshop (SSH Energy), June 16-17, 2025, Zurich, Switzerland. [presentation] ([Synergy: TRANSIENCE](#))
 17. Sandstad, M., Sanderson, B., & Steinert, N. (2025). METEOR: A novel framework for emulating multi-timescale regional climate responses, EGU General Assembly 2025. [presentation] ([Synergy: PROVIDE](#))
 18. Sampedro, J., Khan, Z., Mittal, S., Kikstra, J. (2024). Incorporating equity, gender, health and other co-benefits into NEXUS and IAM research, EGU General Assembly 2024 [ITS3.27/ERE6.6 session] ([Synergy: GRAPHICS, IAM COMPACT](#))
 19. García-Muros, X., Alonso-Epelde, E., González-Eguino, M., and Rodríguez-Zúñiga, A. (2024). Can energy and environmental taxation be progressive in the EU?, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-10785, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-10785>, 2024. [presentation] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT](#))
 20. Van de Ven, D.-J. and Sampedro, J. (2024). Passenger transport decarbonisation under different equity

- considerations, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-19615, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-19615>, 2024. [poster] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT](#))
21. Frilingou, N., van de Ven, D.-J., Mittal, S., Karamaneas, A., Nikolakakis, T., Gardumi, F., Koasidis, K., and Nikas, A. (2024). How do interest rates affect decarbonisation pathways? A stakeholder-driven multi-model analysis., EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-17148, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-17148>, 2024. [poster] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT](#).)
 22. Alonso-Epelde, E., Rodés, C., and Moyano-Reina, M. (2024). MEDUSA – Modelling Equity and DistribUtional impacts for Socioeconomic Analysis. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-5065>, 2024. [poster] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT](#))
 23. Rhodes, C.B., et al. (2023). gcamreport: An R tool to Process and Standardise GCAM Outputs. 2023 GCAM Annual Meeting, June 6-8, 2023 (online) [poster] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT](#))
 24. Sampedro, J. et al. (2023). Residential Energy Demand, Emissions, and Expenditures at Regional and Income-decile Level for Alternative Futures. 2023 GCAM Annual Meeting, June 6-8, 2023 (online) [poster] ([Synergy: GRAPHICS, IAM COMPACT](#))
 25. van de Ven, D.J., et al. (2023). Implementation of Current Policies in GCAM. 2023 GCAM Annual Meeting, June 6-8, 2023 (online) [poster] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT](#))
 26. Nikas, A., Frilingou, N., Heussaff, C., Fragkos, P., Mittal, S., Sampedro, J., Giarola, S., Sasse, J.-P., Rinaldi, L., Doukas, H., Gambhir, A., Giannousakis, A., Golinucci, N., Koasidis, K., Rocco, M. V., Trutnevyte, E., Xexakis, G., Zachmann, G., Zisarou, E., ... Van de Ven, D.-J. (2023). Three corner options for replacing Russian gas imports in Europe: a multi-model analysis. IAMC 2023. [presentation] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT, NDC ASPECTS, MANET](#))
 27. van de Ven, D.-J., Nikas, A., Gambhir, A., Koasidis, K., Elia, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Campagnolo, L., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzo, E., Doukas, H., Fougeyrollas, A., Gargiulo, M., Mouël, P. L., Neuner, F., Perdana, S., Ven, , Vielle, M., Zagamé, P., & Mittal, S. (2023). A multi-model analysis of the EU’s path to net zero. *IAMC 2023*. [presentation] ([Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE, IAM COMPACT](#))
 28. Zhang et al. (2023). “The shifting geopolitics of natural gas: Russia’s invasion of Ukraine and implications for the low-carbon transition”. Sixteenth Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium (IAMC), November 14 - 16, 2023, Venice, Italy. [presentation] ([Synergy: UK Energy Research Centre Phase 4, FCDO-funded Climate Compatible Growth \(CCG\) Programme](#))
 29. Xexakis et al. (2023). “The impacts of a polycrisis on sustainable development: Experts’ vs. modellers’ expectations and the capabilities of IAMs”. Sixteenth Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium (IAMC), November 14 - 16, 2023, Venice, Italy. [poster] ([Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE](#))
 30. Koasidis et al. (2023). “Delving in the impact of stakeholder input in modelled pathways: Canada’s path to net-zero and the role of game-changing innovations”. Sixteenth Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium (IAMC), November 14 - 16, 2023, Venice, Italy. [poster] ([Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE](#))
 31. Boitier, B. et al. (2023). A multi-model assessment of the EU’s path to net zero: aligning near-term action with long-term visions. ECEMP 2023. [presentation] ([Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE, IAM COMPACT](#))
 32. Frilingou, N. et al. (2023). A multi-model assessment of European strategies to eliminate Russian gas imports. ECEMP 2023. [presentation] ([Synergy: IAM COMPACT, NDC ASPECTS, MANET](#))

33. Xexakis G. (2023). Dependency & Energy Security. ECEMP 2023. [session chair] (Synergy: PARIS REINFORCE)

2.3 Joint policy events

So far, DIAMOND has been active co-organising side-events in the Conference of the Parties (COP), along with other research projects and organisations. In UNFCCC's 28th COP (COP 28) in Dubai, DIAMOND co-organised the side-event "Bridging the gap between the 'Fit for 55' package and the 2050 ambition of a net-zero EU economy" at the Greek Pavilion on December 5, 2023, with the Horizon Europe project IAM COMPACT and the Hellenic Society for the Environment and Cultural Heritage. In the 30th COP (COP30) in Belém, DIAMOND co-organised the side-event "Bridging Scientists & Citizens for Climate Action" at the Mediterranean Pavillion on November 21st, 2025, alongside the Euro-Mediterranean Economists Association (EMEA) and the EU co-funded projects C4LA and CROSS-REIS. More details on the two events can be found on our website (see also Figure 3 for the event flyers).

Figure 3. Flyers for the two DIAMOND co-organised side-events at COP28 and COP30

2.4 Capacity development and communication activities

So far, two webinars have been organised by DIAMOND: one on "Stakeholder Participation in IAMs" in February 2025, and another on "The Past and Future of Scenarios in the IPCC" in June 2025. During these webinars, external colleagues joined DIAMOND partners to discuss the themes of each event, reflecting on insights from their activities (e.g., from the TRANSCIENCE project, or insights from a joint, cross-project publication on participatory modelling supported by five EU-funded and three other projects), as well as discussing potential opportunities for future synergies.

At the same time, in parallel with our General Assembly meeting in June 2025, we held a bilateral meeting with our sister project WorldTrans at the premises of MET.No (co-ordinator of WorldTrans), allowing the two consortia to discuss potential activities on synergies as well as together test the interface developed for the FRIDA model.

At the same time, DIAMOND actively participated and supported events organised by the MAIA project, before its conclusion in September 2025; moreover, DIAMOND continues to engage and be part of the interactive synergy map of Climate Research Communication Network (set up by the ESM2025 project), participating in joint webinars and planning to pursue more science communication-related synergies during its final year.

Finally, *capacity development* activities that the project participated in, and which were organised from projects of relevance to DIAMOND, include:

- The Summer School on Integrated Assessment Models: The NAVIGATE and ENGAGE projects, funded by Horizon 2020, are launching a Summer School aimed at providing advanced training for young international scholars, advanced PhD students and early postdoc fellows, working on integrated assessment models. The Summer School will be organised by the RFF-CMCC European Institute on Economics and the Environment (EIEE) and will take place at Lake Como, Villa del Grumello, from 3 to 7 July 2023. The objective of the school is to create a community of young scholars from a broad range of disciplines (climate, ecology, economy, energy, political science) actively working on modelling human activities and the earth system in an integrated framework commonly referred to as Integrated Assessment Modeling. Our partner BC3 has registered and participated in the Summer School.
- The Joint Summer School on Modelling Tools for Sustainable Development: Hosted by the International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP), in July 2023, the school will provide free training, access to discussion forums, and coaching skills in energy planning models and tools. Two of our models will be taught in the school: OSeMOSYS and CLEWs have been encouraged to apply. Our partner Imperial was part of the organisation team and responsible for training sessions, while colleagues from ICCS registered and participated in the Summer School as well.